

Associations between time to appendectomy and postoperative length of stay and complications in patients with acute appendicitis

A protocol for an observational retrospective cohort study

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Background

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common surgical emergencies worldwide, the gold standard treatment being laparoscopic appendectomy, often performed outside regular working hours.¹⁻³ Appendicitis primarily affects a younger, otherwise healthy, population with an eight percent lifetime risk in the Western world.^{1,4,5} The diagnosis of acute appendicitis is determined by intraoperative findings and classified as either uncomplicated or complicated. Complicated appendicitis is defined as a gangrenous or perforated appendix, with or without the presence of intraabdominal abscess.¹ Complicated appendicitis is associated with a higher risk of postoperative morbidity requiring postoperative antibiotic therapy, whereas uncomplicated appendicitis does not require postoperative treatment.^{3,6,7} Both clinical and logistical factors influence the timing of diagnostic laparoscopy for suspected acute appendicitis. Clinical assessment and triage are based on symptom duration, patients' presentation, and potential imaging results, CT or ultrasound.¹ Logistical factors include competing emergency surgeries, as well as safety concerns related to night-time surgery, which may favor postponement until daytime.^{6,8}

Traditionally, all cases of acute appendicitis were considered to progress inevitably to perforation, so immediate surgery was deemed necessary to reduce the risk of morbidity. Studies have reported increased risk of perforation, prolonged length of hospital stay (LOS), and higher readmission rates when appendectomy is delayed beyond 12 hours.^{7,9,10} More recent evidence suggests that uncomplicated and complicated appendicitis are different disease entities, and that perforation is often present at admission rather than caused by a short preoperative delay.^{1-3,11,12} The 2020 World Society of Emergency Surgery guidelines suggest that appendectomy for uncomplicated appendicitis within 24 hours of admission does not increase the risk of complicated appendicitis or morbidity. In contrast, clinically suspected or CT-verified complicated appendicitis should be prioritized within 12 hours.¹ A recent meta-analysis supported these findings but was unable to analyze uncomplicated and complicated appendicitis as subgroups, which limits their conclusion on whether uncomplicated appendicitis may safely tolerate delays beyond 24 hours.³ The association between the timing of appendectomy and patient-centered outcomes remain an important area for further research with contemporary data. The present study will examine postoperative LOS as a surrogate marker of postoperative morbidity and recovery, as well as postoperative complications, and will assess whether the association between timing of appendectomy and the primary outcome differs between uncomplicated and complicated appendicitis.

Aim

To investigate the association between time to appendectomy and postoperative LOS, and the risk of postoperative complications in adults and adolescents with acute appendicitis undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy.

Hypothesis

We hypothesize that acute laparoscopic appendectomy performed within 24 hours from admission is not associated with increased postoperative LOS or risk of postoperative complications.

Methods

This protocol is developed in accordance with the principles outlined in STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology).¹³

Study design

We will conduct a retrospective observational cohort study of patients presenting with acute appendicitis undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy in the Capital Region and the Zealand Region of Denmark.

Data source

Data on the study population will be retrieved from the TRIPLE-A database, established through a large-scale data extraction from the Electronic Health Record system ‘*Sundhedsplatformen* (Epic Systems Corporation, WI, USA)’. The database covers all anesthesia-linked surgical procedures performed at public hospitals in the Capital and Zealand Regions between 1 January 2017 and 1 July 2025, accounting for approximately 1.2 million anesthetic procedures.^{14,15} Clinical data in TRIPLE-A were not collected or registered for research purposes; they were prospectively documented as part of routine care and will subsequently be extracted for retrospective analysis.

Setting and Population

In Denmark, acute appendectomies are exclusively performed in public hospitals. Patients aged ≥ 15 years will be included, as they are physiologically comparable to adults, and there are no anesthetic or surgical differences in their management. The study will include patients operated in the Capital and Zealand Regions, covering a population of approximately 2.8 million individuals. The study population will be identified using the patients’ unique identification number linked to the surgical

procedure code according to the Danish adaptation of the NOMESCO Classification of Surgical Procedures.¹⁶

Inclusion criteria

Patients ≥ 15 years will be eligible for inclusion if they underwent appendectomy for suspected acute appendicitis, defined by the surgical procedure code for laparoscopic appendectomy KJEA01.

Exclusion criteria

Patients are excluded if they:

- Underwent converted surgery from laparoscopic to open appendectomy with the surgical procedure code combination: KJEA00 and KJEA01.
- Underwent laparoscopic appendectomy for indication other than acute appendicitis, such as elective appendectomy, cesarean section and appendectomy or right-sided hemicolectomy and appendectomy.
- Did not have a complete case time log (i.e. missing data on time of admission; referral to the operation room; anesthesia induction; or discharge), or the log could not be recreated using simple predefined code rules.

Exposures and Outcomes

A detailed list of variables is provided in **Appendix 1**.

Outcome measures

Primary outcome

Postoperative length of stay (LOS) from first incision of appendectomy until discharge (hours).

Secondary outcomes

Postoperative stay > 24 hours in the Intensive care unit (ICU) within 30 days (Y/N).

Reoperation within 30 days postoperative (Y/N).

Readmission within 30 days postoperative with a new admission or emergency department contact (Y/N).

Postoperative infection within 30 days requiring hospital contact (Y/N). Defined as postoperative antibiotic treatment at the hospital or an ICD-10 diagnosis code of infection.

Postoperative ultrasound drainage of intra-abdominal abscess within 30 days (Y/N).

Postoperative surgical complications within 30 days according to the Clavien-Dindo Classification (Grade I, II, IIIa, IIIb, IV, V)

Exposure variables

Primary exposure

Time from hospital admission to appendectomy start (hours).

Secondary exposures

Time of day for appendectomy (Day (08-15:59), Evening (16-23:59) or Night (00-07:59)).

Admission outside regular working hours (Y/N). Yes, if hospital admission outside normal work hours (weekday 8-15:59).

Complicated appendicitis (Y/N). Yes, if treated with antibiotics between 24 to 48 hours postoperative. As a surrogate for the intraoperative diagnosis of complicated appendicitis and following three days antibiotic ordination performed by the operator.

Preoperative antibiotic treatment within 24 hours (Y/N). Yes, if administration of antibiotics between hospital admission to surgery start.

Preoperative radiology (CT or ultrasound) (Y/N). Yes, if radiology imaging was performed between hospital admission to surgery start.

Baseline variables

The following patient demographics will be retrieved for baseline statistics: age, sex, BMI (Kg/m²), American Society of Anesthesiology classification (I-V), preoperative leukocytes (x10⁹), C-reactive protein level (mg/L) and creatinine counts (µmol/L), preoperative fever (Y/N) if body temperature is >38°C, preoperative opiate administration (Y/N), smoking status (never, former, current), location (hospital site) and number of comorbidities at admission (None, 1, 2, 3, ≥4).

Data handling

Data will be anonymized prior to analysis to ensure patient confidentiality and compliance with data protection regulations. Before receiving the complete dataset, researchers will carefully validate data samples by comparing the extracted information with the data recorded in the Electronic Health Record system. Derived variables will be constructed from existing data, including composite measures and surrogate variables. Surrogate variables will use reliably recorded information as indirect indicators of clinical conditions that are otherwise inconsistently documented in health records. Before analysis, the dataset will undergo preprocessing with checks for missing data, duplicate records, and implausible clinical values, which will be addressed using predefined cutoffs. The study will use only validated data, ensuring that analyses are based on reliable and accurate information. Data will be stored in a secure database with restricted access, available to members of the research team. The anonymized dataset will be retained for a specified period and then deleted after the study is completed.

Ethical consideration

The initial TRIPLE-A database extraction has been approved by ‘Team for Medical Record Data, Research Ethics and Research Support, Capital Region of Denmark’ (*Approval number R-23038250; 14 July 2023*). Furthermore, approval has been granted for the transfer of medical record data from the database to this research project (*Approval number R-25043111; 24 June 2025*).

Statistical Analysis

Baseline characteristics will be summarized using descriptive statistics. Normality of continuous variables will be assessed through inspection of histograms. Continuous variables will be reported as mean with standard deviation (SD) if normally distributed, or as median with interquartile range (IQR) if non-normally distributed. Categorical variables will be presented as counts and percentages.

The primary analysis will utilize a linear regression model to examine the relationship between the primary outcome, postoperative LOS, and the primary exposure time from hospital admission to appendectomy start, along with predefined secondary exposures. To reduce potential bias, regression models will be adjusted for the predefined adjusting variables as stated above. Results will be presented as estimated mean differences in postoperative LOS (hours) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals.

Secondary dichotomous outcomes will be analyzed using logistic regression models, with the same exposures and adjusting variables as for the primary outcome. The results will be presented as odds ratios (OR) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals.

A sensitivity analysis will be conducted using the time interval from booking of surgery to appendectomy start as an alternative exposure, to assess its potential association with the primary outcome. Furthermore, we will perform subgroup analysis to assess whether the association with the primary outcome differs between uncomplicated and complicated appendicitis.

All statistical tests will be two-tailed, and a p-value <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

All analyses will be conducted using the most recent stable version of R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

Appendix

Appendix 1: Variable table

Primary outcome			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Postoperative length of stay (LOS)	Hours, as a continuous variable.	Postoperative LOS, up to 30 days after discharge.	From surgery start until hospital discharge.
Secondary outcomes			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Postoperative stay > 24 hours in the Intensive care unit (ICU) within 30 days (Y/N).	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as postoperative ICU stay >24 hours within 30 days.	Postoperative 30 days
Reoperation within 30 days postoperative	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as reoperation 30 days postoperative new operation (“new surgical event”) registered in the journal system.	0-30 days postoperative
Readmission within 30 days postoperative	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as readmission 30 days postoperative thereby having a new admission or emergency department contact.	0-30 days after discharge
Postoperative infection within 30 days requiring hospital contact	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as (1) antibiotic treatment administered at the hospital within 3-30 days postoperative OR 2) a diagnosis of infection within 30 days postoperative, identified by ICD-10 codes from the primary admission or readmission: postoperative infection (T81.4.x), pneumonia (J13.x-J18.x), Cystitis (N30.x, N39.0), sepsis (R65.x A40.x, A41.x), C. difficile (A04.7).	Postoperative 30 days

<p>Postoperative ultrasound drainage of intra-abdominal abscess within 30 days</p>	<p>Binary variable (Y/N)</p>	<p>Postoperative ultrasound reports freetext combination search of; "absces" OR "intraperitoneal" OR "byld" OR "abces" OR "pus" OR "ansamling" AND "ultralyd" OR "UL" OR "UL-vejledt" OR "Ul vejledt" OR "punktur" OR "dræn" OR "drænage" OR "perkutan" OR "drænanlæggelse" OR "abscesdrænage" OR "ultralydsvejledt"; with negation criteria for MRI, CT and X-ray.</p>	<p>Postoperative 30 days</p>
<p>Postoperative surgical complications 30 days according to the Clavien-Dindo Classification</p>	<p>Categorical variable (I, II, III, IV, V)</p>	<p>Defined as any adverse event within 30 days post operative according to the Clavien-Dindo classification: <u>I = Prolonged postoperative LOS > 1 day, Readmission, Acute kidney failure</u> <i>(Minor deviation without intervention (permitted medication, bedside wound care)).</i> <u>II = Postoperative antibiotic treatment within 30 days</u> <i>(Pharmacological treatment (antibiotics, transfusion)).</i> <u>IIIa = Postoperative ultrasound drainage of intra-abdominal abscess within 30 days</u> <i>(Intervention without general anesthesia.)</i> IIIb = Reoperation within 30 days postoperative <i>(Intervention under general anesthesia.)</i> IV = Postoperative admission to the Intensive care unit (ICU) within 30 days <i>(Life-threatening complication with organ failure requiring IC/ICU treatment.)</i> V = All-cause mortality 30 days postoperative <i>(Death.)</i></p>	<p>Postoperative 30 days</p>

All-cause mortality 30 days postoperative	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as all-cause mortality 30 days postoperative	Postoperative 30 days
Acute kidney failure	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as serum creatinine increase of more than 26.5 µmol/L within a period of less than 48 hours or an increase in serum creatinine > 1.5 times the baseline defined as the most recent measurement within the past 14 days. (KDIGO definition, as a surrogate for acute kidney failure)	Postoperative 30 days
Exposure variables			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Time to appendectomy start	Categorical variable	From arriving time in the emergency department until the start of surgery <8, 8-16, 16-24, 24-36, > 36 hours	Admission to start of surgery
Time from booking of surgery to appendectomy start	Categorical variable	From booking of surgery by abdominal surgeon until start of surgery <3, 3-6, 6-12, 12-24, > 24 hours	Booking to start of surgery
Time of day for appendectomy	Categorical variable (Day, evening or nightshift)	Defined as surgery start: Day (08-15:59), Evening (16-23:59) or Nightshift (00-07:59)	Surgery start
Admission outside regular working hours (Y/N)	Binary variable (Y/N)	Outside regular working hours defined by weekday evenings (16:00–23:59), weekday nightshifts (00:00–07:59), or any weekend (Friday 16:00–Monday 07:59). Regular working hours Monday–Friday 08:00–15:59.	At admission
Complicated appendicitis	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as receiving antibiotics (iv or po) between 24 to 48 hours postoperative as a surrogate for the intraoperative diagnosis of complicated appendicitis and following ordination of 3 days postoperative AB treatment.	Postoperative 0-3 days

Preoperative radiology (CT or ultrasound)	Categorical variable (None / Ultrasound / CT / CT + Ultrasound)	Defined as preoperative radiology type performed (None / Ultrasound / CT / CT + Ultrasound).	From admission to surgery
Baseline variables			
Age	As a continuous variable, Years		At admission
Sex	Categorical variable	Defined as male or female	At admission
Weight	As a continuous variable, Kilograms (Kg)	Values below 20 kg or above 250 kg will be considered as registration errors and will be excluded from the analysis.	At admission
Height	As a continuous variable, Centimeters (cm)	Values below 100 or above 210 cm will be considered as registration errors and will be excluded from the analysis.	At admission
BMI	As a continuous variable, Kg/m ²	Values below 10 or above 60 Kg/m ² will be considered as registration errors and will be excluded from the analysis.	At admission
ASA-score	Categorical variable: ASA I, II, III, IV-V	ASA score is taken from the preoperative anesthetic assessment, otherwise from surgical plan. Categorized into following groups: <u>I, II, III, IV-V</u> ASA I: Healthy patient, ASA II: Mild systemic disease, ASA III: Severe systemic disease, ASA IV: Severe systemic disease with constant threat to life, ASA V: Moribund patient	At admission

Preoperative C-reactive protein level, CRP	As a continuous variable	Defined as the highest measured C-reactive protein level (mg/L) preoperatively	Preoperative within 24 hours
Preoperative fever	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as the highest temperature (°C) measured preoperatively and as fever when body temperature >38°C.	Preoperative within 24 hours
Preoperative leukocytes	As a continuous variable	Defined as leukocytes x10 ⁹ /L measured preoperatively	Preoperative within 24 hours
Preoperative creatinine	As a continuous variable	Defined as creatinine µmol/L measured preoperatively	Preoperative within 24 hours
Preoperative antibiotics	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defined as received antibiotics (iv/p.o) preoperatively	Administered preoperative within 24 hours
Preoperative opioids	Binary variable (Y/N)	Defines as received opioid (iv/p.o) preoperatively	Administered preoperative within 24 hours
Location (Hospital)	OPIAD def.	Locations categorized in The Capital Region (Site A-I) and Zealand Region (Site J-P) of Denmark.	At admission
Number of comorbidities at admission	Categorical variable: 1, 2, 3, ≥4	Categorized in number of comorbidities at baseline: 1, 2, 3, ≥4 ICD-codes: Crohn's disease (K50.x), Ulcerative colitis (K51.x), Other non-infectious colitis (K52.x), Diverticulitis (K57.x), Irritable bowel syndrome, IBS (K58.x), Celiac disease (K90.0), Rheumatoid arthritis (M05.x, M06.x), Systemic lupus erythematosus, SLE (M32.x), Other autoimmune diseases (M30.x–M36.x), Epilepsy (G40.x), Multiple sclerosis (G35), Coagulation	At admission

		<p>disorders (D65–D69), Anemia (D50–D64), Pervasive developmental disorders (F84.x), Hypertension (I10, I11, I12, I13, I14, I15), Osteoporosis (M80, M81, M82, M83), Diabetes (E10, E11, E12, E13, E14), Congestive heart failure (I50.x), Ischemic heart disease (I21.x, I22.x, I24.x, I25.x), Arrhythmia (I47.x, I48.x, I49.x), Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, COPD (J44), Cancer (C00–C97), Chronic kidney disease (N18), Cerebrovascular disease (I61.x, I63.x, I64.x), Mild liver disease (K70.x, K71.x, K73.x, K74.x, K76.x), Moderate/severe liver disease (K72.x, I85.x), Alcohol-related disease (F10.x), Drug-related disease (F11.x, F12.x, F13.x, F14.x, F16.x), Dementia (F00, F01, F02, F03), Parkinson’s disease (G20), Depression (F32.x–F33.x), Anxiety (F40.x–F41.x), Schizophrenia (F20.x).</p>	
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